

The Ammines of Nickel(II) Cyanide

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Many compounds are now known to have been formed by treating nickel cyanide with concentrated ammonia solution. Bernouilli and Grether¹ reported a complex $[\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2\text{NH}]_2$ containing a molecule of water. Hertel *et al.*² studied a new compound, $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2\cdot\text{NH}_3$, with variable quantities of water. Stability was determined by measuring and comparing vapour pressures and analyses of the compounds gave the volume relationships in their formation. Kocsis³ obtained some simple nickel-hexammine and -tetrammine compounds with water of hydration. Various K and NH_4 nickel-ammine double salts were prepared⁴ which decomposed on dissolving in water. In the air, these compounds lost ammonia more rapidly than simple salts consisting of the same anions. Examination of complex Ni-hexammines showed that the concentration of solutions or mixtures had some relation to the structure of the complex compound formed⁵. Cambi *et al.*⁶ measured the susceptibility of many known nickel cyanide complexes. Hofmann and Höchtlen⁷ stated that an ammoniacal nickel cyanide solution, after keeping for a day or so, deposited small crystals of $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Aynsley *et al.*⁸ attempted to prepare the ammines of nickel cyanide by the above method. No crystals were formed at the end of a week; but when the mixture was kept overnight at 5°, large, deep blue needles separated. They reported the formation of unstable $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2\cdot 4\text{NH}_3\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and stable $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2\cdot\text{NH}_3\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Rayner and coworker⁹ in attempted repetitions of Hofmann and Höchtlen's work found no crystals in the first few weeks, but one solution in the course of a year deposited a hydrated nickel cyanide-ammonia complex. This consisted of small crystals in spherical aggregates of about 2 mm in diameter and some single crystals, about 0.25 mm long.

During the studies of clathrate compounds, reactions of ammonia with nickel cyanide were also observed in our laboratory. Following Evans *et al.*¹⁰, ammoniacal nickel cyanide solution was placed in a covered bottle. The formation of crystals was not observed for a few weeks. After a considerable time, small blue-red crystals were noticed at the bottom of the bottle. The reaction was allowed to carry on for about five months. When the bottle

1. *Chem. Ztg.*, 1901, 25, 436.
2. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1920, 178, 202.
3. *Magyar Chem. Folyóirat*, 1934, 40, 147; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1935, II, 494.
4. *Ibid.*, 1928, 34, 213.
5. *Ibid.*, 1928, 33, 34.
6. *Gazzetta*, 1934, 64, 758.
7. *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1149.
8. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4137.
9. *Ibid.*, 1958, 3412.
10. *Ibid.*, 1950, 3346.

was uncovered, a strong smell of ammonia in the violet-coloured solution was noticed. A heavy deposit of purple crystals was obtained. The crystals were washed with ethanol and ether. After pressing once lightly between filter papers, these were dried in a desiccator containing anhydrous calcium chloride for one day. The compound was found to be $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2 \cdot \text{NH}_3$. [Found: C, 19.03; H, 2.73; N, 32.67. Calc. for $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2 \cdot \text{NH}_3$: C, 18.75; H, 2.34; N, 32.81%].

In the attempted formation of furan clathrate, one very interesting result was observed. Instead of getting the furan clathrate, a hydrated nickel cyanide-ammonia complex, $\text{Ni}(\text{CN})_2 \cdot \text{NH}_3 \cdot \frac{1}{2} \text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained. (Found: C, 19.06; H, 2.68; N, 31.65. Calc.: C, 18.2; H, 2.7; N, 31.8%). This may be due to the decomposition of the furan clathrate taking place by the escape of furan in presence of water vapour.

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